

Tactile sensors for Material recognition in Social and Collaborative Robots: A brief review

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Abstract— Touch sensing is helpful and important for a robot to understand and have bidirectional physical contact with its environment, particularly objects it interacts with. Sensors provide information to robot systems about their surrounding environment in order to help them to achieve dynamic interaction tasks, as an example in bionic prostheses, in teleoperation or in robots that should autonomously take decisions according to the situation. To this end, several tactile and vision-based solutions have been adopted in robotics over the past few decades enabled by the improvements of the functional and metrological performances of state of the art sensors, which have been widely reported in the literature. In an effort to gather and summarize a selection of scientific and technological advances in this field, this brief review proposes a categorization based on addressed tasks with tactile sensors. Specifically, it outlines a selection of current trends in material and shape recognition, and encoding of textural and compliance properties, by sensorized robots. Selected tactile sensor technologies are discussed with their applications to achieve specific tasks, also in combination with other sensors. Finally, touch exploration strategies are discussed briefly. This review identifies unresolved challenges and suggests future trends for the application of tactile sensors in various jobs.

Keywords—tactile sensors, material recognition, robots, touch, computer vision, robotics

I. INTRODUCTION

Touch abilities could enable robots to sense and represent the environment to interact, by gathering mechanothermal information during exploration. The aim that prompts the application of tactile sensors is thus to integrate in intelligent machines the skills that assist humans to understand their surroundings by means of physical contact and to interact safely [1]. Based on background literature, human touch is the elective sense to understand object shapes and material characteristics [2]. Similarly to humans, it is therefore important to confer touch abilities to robots in order to enable environmental awareness, to steer away from possibly harmful impacts, and to offer data for further activities like in-hand manipulation. Awareness of the surrounding environment is important for the robot to take decisions. Previous reports of our group reviewed tactile sensing from various technological viewpoints, including microfabricated sensors with capacitive, piezoelectric and piezoresistive transducers [3], with Fiber Bragg Gratings (FBGs) [4], and

bio-hybrid and fully biological approaches [5]. In this brief review, existing literature is analyzed by breaking down the perception process into steps to describe the overall process of detecting and analyzing item attributes via physical senses. A general illustration of a touch-based sensory system is shown in Figure 1 [6]–[8], to obtain information on object attributes like material and shape, and delivering information that are action-related, like object slippage detection and localization. In Figure 1-left, the touch sensing procedure is organized into blocks that show distinct levels of sensing, perception, along with action. Figure 1-right illustrates the hardware blocks, relating them to their functionality.

Figure 1. Robotic tactile system hierarchical structural (right) and functional (left) block diagram, adapted from [8] (©[2008] IEEE).

A sensor-based system transforms stimuli that are external (such as vibration, pressure and heat) into changes of the detecting components (transducers, low-level in the

hierarchy) of tactile sensors [6], [7]. This information is conditioned, collected, and handled by a data processing unit (that may be embedded) before being sent to the level of perception (high-level in the hierarchy) to build a global model and observe the qualities of interacting items (e.g., structure and the properties of a material). Touch sensitivity can be combined with different sensory modalities like visual and audio-based perception. Control instructions are finally used in order to implement the required actions.

As widely detailed in background studies [9]–[12], the last decades have seen considerable development in the progress of touch sensors, involving fabrication procedures and materials. The study of how to analyze tactile data to retrieve the input data contained, mostly in the detection of the object and the localization, is gaining traction these days also thanks to the wide adoption of artificial intelligence strategies applied to robotic machines [13]. Moreover, touch requires dedicated solutions for achieving elaboration of tactile sensory data that are produced by transducers which are spread through the body: this is a peculiar feature of somatosensation.

This assessment briefly examines the advances in the artificial ability to encode the tactile attributes of an object, such as classification of a material, and recognition of an object, in order to aid the progress of research in retrieval of information from tactile sensory input. Research that blends touch sensing with different sensory modalities, such as movement and vision sensors, is being investigated as well.

II. RECOGNITION OF MATERIAL BY TACTILE SENSING

One of the most crucial indications that a robot needs, in order to properly interact with its environment, is the material quality of the surface of an object. The use of vision to recognize object material has become increasingly popular [14]–[17]. Vision, on the other hand, can detect an earlier identified surface material but does not evaluate its physical-mechanical parameters on its own. It is thus of paramount importance to use touch sensitivity to complement sensory experience in classifying the properties of a material. Surface texture (roughness and friction) and compliance are two of the important factors for handling things. Based on these clues, humans are exceptionally adept at detecting object material qualities [18] (a thorough examination of how humans perceive material features is discussed in [19]). Researchers have attempted to make robots capable of identifying material qualities with skills equivalent to those of humans. Surface texture-based attributes and object stiffness-based properties are the two types of properties that can be classified and that will be discussed in the next sections.

A. Tactile material recognition based on surface texture

The friction that occurs at the sensor contact, while it slides across an item exterior, is utilized in order to identify the surface material. The utilization of acoustic signals generated by friction to distinguish object materials is one of these technologies that are low-cost and requires little computer resources [20]. In [21] a microphone is installed on a leg of a robot that taps on the floor as the robot walks, much like a person who is blind tapping his/her cane. The tapping

signature is later utilized to categorize various materials of the floor. In [22], to identify various textures, an artificial finger along with a microphone is utilized to capture data of a sound that is transformed to the frequency domain by utilizing Fast Fourier Transform (FFT). Identification of textures is presented in [23] using Self-Organizing Maps (SOMs) and a microphone-based texture sensor. Auditory signals utilization has the advantages of being cheaper and requiring little computing; nevertheless, ambient and motor noise may degrade identification ability.

B. Tactile material recognition based on object stiffness

In [24] a leg of a robot is used to tap on the surface of an object and sensor data, hardness and elasticity are analyzed, also it can reveal the stiffness of an object. In [25], [26], the proposed technology allowed estimating the hardness of the object by processing GelSight’s tactile image sequence sensor. In [27] dynamic time warping is utilized using the moment of the image of the tactile sign as a symbol, to match similarities between a signal of time series to categorize objects as hard or deformable. Force sensors used for mechanical checks, blocking stretch and tightness are discussed in [28]. A sensing device that is multi-indenting is proposed in [29] to measure the hardness of the tested material objects.

III. SHAPE PERCEPTION OF TACTILE OBJECT

Shape perception is the potential to classify or remake the shape of an object, with the ability to implement various tasks, from getting the exact structure obtaining the point cloud of the object, shape element identification or complete profile. As an example, this is implemented in multiple daily-life operations such as manipulation while drinking to get structural data about the object. With artificial intelligence strategies, as several shapes are experienced, robots gain skills to plan and execute. However, shape features are unable to be observed in bad illumination conditions or in case of vision occluded by the hand or other obstacles. In contrast, such factors cannot create any problem when dealing with tactile sensors. The rise of novel families of touch sensors offers upward thrust to the appearance and fast spread of algorithms to detect object shapes, both local and global (Figure 2), by utilizing tactile sensors.

Figure 2. Two balls that have various shapes: one is known as tennis ball and the other known as golf ball. Generally, both are balls. However, at local scale, (a) consist of pits that are small and (b) has a curved shape.

IV. EXPLORATION STRATEGIES TO ENCODE TACTILE PROPERTIES WITH SENSORIZED ROBOTS

A. Bayesian tactile exploration and sensing strategies

The Shadow Dexterous Hand was used in [30] to combine multimodal touch sensing (force, temperature and vibration) and train the robot to perform exploratory motions comparable to those made by humans when recognizing items based on their compliance, texture, and thermal qualities. When recognizing an object, exploratory motions are executed using a strategy called Bayesian exploration [31]. Each BioTac is made up of a hard core that houses a grid of 19 electrodes that is encased in an elastic skin. An immiscible and conducting fluid is used to inflate the skin. The liquid is moved when the skin comes into contact with an item, leading to distributed conductance shifts inside the electrode array on the rigid interface of the core. A schematic diagram of the BioTac cross-sectional sensor can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Schematic of the BioTac Cross-sectional sensor [32] (©[2016] IEEE).

The characteristics of the 10 objects that were used in validation and for the training of the system to identify objects with the help of touch are shown in Figure 4 [30]. Dataset collection and training were performed and the real-time tactile data collection and processing were completed and stored in text files as system memory.

The results of validation experiments with Bayesian exploration revealed that the algorithm only failed once in ten attempts of object recognition on each object, resulting in a 99 percent success rate. Due to its similar compliance, the soft sponge was mistakenly recognized as a feather in one failure (Figure 5). Copper, brick, acrylic and wood (items from 1–3 and item 10) have small compliance, since they are rigid items, while the other objects have greater compliance, thus

enabling the discrimination along with the compliance feature. Analysis of the variance of the filtered vibration signal allows discriminating textures with high variance (brick, foam, wood and damp sponge, i.e., 2, 4, 6, and 10) as objects that are rough, whereas copper, acrylic, toy, plush, feather, soft foam and silicone (objects 1, 3, 5, 7, 8, 9) are identified as objects that are smooth. Several objects had discernible conductive qualities in the thermal tests, with the exception of the foam, feather, soft foam and plush toy (objects 5, 6, 7, and 9), which are all thermal insulators. Therefore, the three features used, compliance, texture roughness and thermal conductivity, created a space of features that enabled the proposed discrimination task.

Properties	acrylic	brick
Compliance	-	-
Texture Roughness	-	+
Thermal Conductivity	0	+
	copper	damp sponge
-	+	+
-	+	-
++	+	-
	soft foam	plush toy
+	+	+
+	-	-
-	-	+
	foam	wood
0	-	
+	+	
-	0	

Figure 4. Total ten objects that are utilized in the identification task [30] (©[2013] IEEE).

B. Artificial curiosity tactile exploration and sensing strategies

A curiosity-driven reinforcement learning technique is presented in [33] that automatically learns a range of motor abilities rather than constructing customized algorithms for completing a particular tactile task. In this method, data of sensory incoming signals drive skill acquisition.

In [34], a novel framework based on reinforcement learning is proposed for real-time motion planning for a humanoid curious agent. In order to represent large regions, compact Markov models are used. To minimize uncertainty, an object recognition approach that employs a three-fingered based hand of a robot that actively explores intriguing object locations is presented in [35]. To iteratively build information from robot touch, a unique probabilistic perception technique is presented using a Bayesian framework. Familiarity and originality exploration behaviors intelligently guide the robot hand to go toward regions with high and low degrees of

interest, respectively, in order to find better positions for perception. These are active behaviors that allow robots to independently investigate sites they feel hold valuable information for recognition, comparable to human exploration methods. For robots to reuse, store and acquire skills, the Continual Curiosity-driven Skill Acquisition (CCSA) system was proposed in [36] for gaining skills and abstractions in an online and continuous manner.

		Identified As									
		Acrylic'	Brick'	Copper'	Damp'sponge'	Feather'	Rough'foam'	Plush'toy'	Silicone'	Soc'foam'	Wood'
Actual Object'	Acrylic'	10'	0'	0'	0'	0'	0'	0'	0'	0'	0'
	Brick'	0'	10'	0'	0'	0'	0'	0'	0'	0'	0'
	Copper'	0'	0'	10'	0'	0'	0'	0'	0'	0'	0'
	Damp'Sponge'	0'	0'	0'	9'	1'	0'	0'	0'	0'	0'
	Feather'	0'	0'	0'	0'	10'	0'	0'	0'	0'	0'
	Rough'Foam'	0'	0'	0'	0'	0'	10'	0'	0'	0'	0'
	Plush'Toy'	0'	0'	0'	0'	0'	0'	10'	0'	0'	0'
	Silicone'	0'	0'	0'	0'	0'	0'	0'	10'	0'	0'
	Soc'Foam'	0'	0'	0'	0'	0'	0'	0'	0'	10'	0'
	Wood'	0'	0'	0'	0'	0'	0'	0'	0'	0'	10'

Figure 5. After the reinforcement learning and training a confusion matrix was created for 10 trials of all 10 objects [30] (©[2013] IEEE).

C. Brain-inspired tactile exploration and sensing strategies

A multiple stage processing of delicate tactile input in closed-loop activity is presented in [37] as a unique neuro-robotic approach for robotic systems and provides the groundwork for the construction and deployment of neuro-mimetic structure for robotic precise tactile discrimination.

To convert analog sensor outputs, resulting from skin deformations, into spike trains, a network of spiking neurons is used in [38]. Then, inside the cuneate nucleus of an artificial brainstem, second order neurons are modelled to implement the strategies mimicking how mechanoreceptor responses might be processed before being transmitted to higher order locations.

Biomimetic spiking responses using fingertip touch sensors to detect release, contact and slide of an item gripped by a prosthetic hand are developed in [39]. Also in [40], the system identifies 18 metal surface textures detected at a constant speed in two directions and show that their strategy outperforms a default model that did not employ the aforementioned extraction of the features. The proposed method achieves real-time detection by utilizing neuromorphic hardware.

Recent trends include neuromorphic solutions [41] by implementing machine mechanoreceptors for material recognition by injecting raw sensor outputs into an artificial neuron model (such as the Izhikevich one) [42] and using

machine intelligence to achieve discrimination of textures by a robotic system [31], [43], [44] or neurostimulation to restore tactile abilities in human amputees by means of bionic limb prostheses [45]–[47].

V. CONCLUSION

Over the last several years, the fast development of tactile devices has opened up new ways for using touch sensing in a variety of robotic systems. Not only should the variety of touch sensors be examined for a given system, but also the most appropriate computing way for decoding the data. Simultaneously, it has brought to light a multitude of issues related to the appropriate use of touch data. This paper highlights the recognition of the shape and surface texture of tactile objects, as well as estimating their pose. Future work can be focused on analyzing latest trends in tactile sensors and investigating their utilization in different tasks.

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